

Performance of 5460ps in Fujian, China, 1988.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Exserted stigma (%)	Resistance score				
							Blast	Bacterial blight	Brown planthopper	Bacterial leaf streak	Grassy stunt
5460ps	125	76.5	13.6	108.3	23.0	46.2	1	1	2	3	3
IR54	150	90.0	11.7	121.0	23.1	42.3	1	1	2	3	3

5460ps has high resistance to major diseases and insects, high-yielding agrocharacters, and good quality. Its

floral characters influencing outcrossing are also good (see table).

The critical stage of sterility-

transformation is about 10 Jul and fertility-transformation 10 Sep under conditions in Fuzhou (26°N). □

New japonica hybrid developed in China

Lo Shao-He and Li Ren-Hua, Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center, Changsha, Hunan, China

76-27A/PC312, a newly developed long-duration (130 d) japonica cross, has erect flag leaves, large panicles, and heavy grain. It shows moderate resistance to blast and bacterial blight. It has 90-cm plant height, 125 spikelets/panicle, and 70-80% seed set. A thousand grains weigh 26 g.

In yield trials in 1985 in 8 locations in northern Hunan, it averaged 6.3 t/ha (see table), 11.3% more than check Aiking 23. In farmers' fields in Shang-Tan in 1986, it outyielded Shan-you 63.

Seed production for the combination is easy; no split sowing is needed. It can yield 3 t hybrid seeds/ha. It is suitable for intermediate-fertility soils, for both single- or double-cropping seasons. □

Yield performance of japonica hybrid at 8 locations in Hunan, China, 1985.

Location	Yield (t/ha)		LSD	
	Hybrid ^a	Check	At 5%	At 1%
Changde	6.3	6.05	0.4	0.5
Yueyang	5.5	5.24	0.4	0.6
Miluo	6.5**	5.61	0.5	0.7
Taojiang	5.3	4.83	0.5	0.7
Xihu	7.4**	6.85	0.4	0.6
Huarong	6.3**	5.98	0.9	0.9
Wangcheng	6.8	6.23	0.3	0.6
Changsha	6.4**	4.62	1.4	1.6
Av	6.3**	5.68		

^a** = significant at 1%.

Effects of storage on rice germplasm viability

P. K. Sinha, J. S. Chauhan, V. S. Chauhan, K. Prasad, and K. Srinivasulu, Central Rainfed Upland Rice Research Station (CRURRS), Hazaribag 825301, India

In most breeding programs that lack storage facilities, germplasm is

maintained by periodical regeneration. Growing out all germplasm accessions every year takes extensive resources. We studied genotypic differences in germination under conventional storage conditions over 30 mo, to identify genotypes that retain viability longer.

Seeds of 24 varieties were obtained from the International Rice Germplasm Center in Nov 1984. Initial germination

Table 1. Ranges and means of temperature and relative humidity during storage, CRURRS, Hazaribag, India.

Month	Year	Relative humidity (%)		Temperature (°C)	
		Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Nov	1984	12 - 93	63.23 ± 1.87	7.0 - 29.0	19.50 ± 0.40
Dec	1984	14 - 88	52.31 ± 1.23	5.0 - 28.0	16.77 ± 0.24
Jan	1985	31 - 100	72.40 ± 2.25	7.0 - 27.0	16.35 ± 0.25
Feb	1985	32 - 100	63.02 ± 1.54	5.0 - 29.0	17.63 ± 0.28
Mar	1985	50 - 91	76.40 ± 1.18	13.0 - 38.0	25.64 ± 0.35
Apr	1985	28 - 84	57.42 ± 1.47	18.0 - 41.0	29.80 ± 0.37
May	1985	28 - 100	66.05 ± 1.83	20.0 - 43.0	30.27 ± 0.46
Jun	1985	55 - 100	84.67 ± 2.41	22.5 - 40.8	30.59 ± 0.37
Jul	1985	90 - 100	95.13 ± 0.52	22.1 - 32.0	26.25 ± 0.23
Aug	1985	88 - 100	96.03 ± 0.63	22.8 - 32.8	26.96 ± 0.24
Sep	1985	82 - 100	94.23 ± 0.92	21.8 - 32.2	26.40 ± 0.14
Oct	1985	87 - 100	84.23 ± 1.92	14.5 - 32.5	24.04 ± 0.50
Nov	1985	35 - 90	74.70 ± 2.02	10.4 - 28.0	20.19 ± 0.35
Dec	1985	53 - 100	79.56 ± 2.16	8.3 - 26.1	17.62 ± 0.36
Jan	1986	46 - 95	63.81 ± 1.83	5.9 - 26.5	16.31 ± 0.47
Feb	1986	44 - 94	62.29 ± 1.98	10.0 - 30.2	19.12 ± 0.30
Mar	1986	24 - 63	47.20 ± 1.83	13.9 - 39.5	24.92 ± 0.5 1
Apr	1986	29 - 71	48.97 ± 1.73	18.3 - 40.0	29.72 ± 0.38
May	1986	37 - 100	58.19 ± 2.59	19.5 - 40.0	29.42 ± 0.31
Jun	1986	35 - 96	70.73 ± 4.12	22.5 - 41.5	29.84 ± 0.63
Jul	1986	66 - 95	82.68 ± 1.25	22.4 - 32.3	26.04 ± 0.27
Aug	1986	65 - 92	81.23 ± 1.38	22.4 - 33.2	26.72 ± 0.18
Sep	1986	65 - 95	81.27 ± 1.72	20.0 - 33.3	26.07 ± 0.44
Oct	1986	41 - 100	79.44 ± 1.19	17.0 - 31.0	24.73 ± 0.29
Nov	1986	50 - 90	70.07 ± 1.68	13.5 - 29.5	21.41 ± 0.38
Dec	1986	53 - 94	71.03 ± 1.72	8.8 - 24.5	16.93 ± 0.26
Jan	1987	49 - 75	62.58 ± 1.40	6.9 - 24.3	15.67 ± 0.34
Feb	1987	56 - 68	61.29 ± 0.74	10.1 - 30.0	20.25 ± 0.37
Mar	1987	45 - 71	55.52 ± 1.20	14.0 - 35.8	24.36 ± 0.47
Apr	1987	37 - 15	52.03 ± 1.72	18.0 - 39.3	29.02 ± 0.34
May	1987	42 - 80	53.52 ± 1.85	18.5 - 41.0	30.54 ± 0.64

at 14% moisture content was 86-92%.

The seeds were stored in paper bags, with the top folded twice and clipped, on wooden shelves Nov 1984-May 1987. Average and maximum and minimum room temperatures and relative humidity during storage are given in Table 1. A 300-seed sample was randomly drawn for each variety in May 1987; one-half of each sample was dehulled. The seeds were put in petri dishes on moist filter paper at room temperature for germination, with 50 seeds constituting a replication.

In general, germination percentage dropped over 30 mo storage. However, there was not much variation in germination between hulled and dehulled seeds. The varieties could be grouped into 3 classes on the basis of germination percentage: no germination, less than 25% germination, and more than 25% germination (Table 2).

Germination ranged from 0 (Salumpikit, Dourado Precoce) to 40% (IR10004-1-1-2), suggesting genetical control for this trait.

These genotypic differences could be used to save the effort of growing out

Table 2. Germination of 24 rice varieties before and after storage. Hazaribag, India.

Variety	Initial germination (%)	Germination (%) after 30 mo	
		Hulled grain	Dehulled grain
IR12919-24-1-8	88	39	38
IR10004-1-1-2	90	40	35
IR27095-20-3	92	35	37
IR6023-10-1-1	92	18	20
IR10120-7-2-1-4	92	22	16
Kinandang Patong	86	20	16
IAC47	89	12	10
IR54	92	8	7
IRAT13	87	7	6
IR38	90	6	6
AC540	90	6	6
H105	87	4	4
IRAT110	88	3	2
CR125-12-8	92	0	0
IAC25	92	0	0
IR34	92	0	0
IRAT109	92	0	0
Kulu	91	0	0
Ngoba	90	0	0
IRAT116	90	0	0
IRAT10	88	0	0
IAC165	88	0	0
Salumpikit	86	0	0
Dourado Precoce	86	0	0

entire germplasm collections every year. Varieties showing more than 25% germination could be stored for 2 yr and regenerated the third year. Genotypes

like IR12979-24-1-8, IR27095-20-3, and IR10004-1-1-2 could be used as donors for long storage life. □

Genetics

Isozyme polymorphism for *Est-2* locus observed at rice vegetative and reproductive phases

R. V. Kumar and S. S. Virmani, IRRI

We analyzed IR36 and IR64 (indicas) and Taichung 65 (japonica) for isozyme polymorphism at vegetative and reproductive phases using three isozyme loci (*Est-2*, *Amp-3*, and *Pgi-2*). The analysis was to determine the allelic constitution for various isozyme loci used to study linkage relationships with the wide compatibility gene (*Sⁿ*). Isozyme polymorphism in the three cultivars is presented in the table.

Taichung 65 showed differential behavior of *Est-2* alleles at the vegetative

(*Est-2⁰*) and reproductive phases (*Est-2²*). Recently, differential behavior of *Est-2* alleles was reported in cold-tolerant rices. Cultivars possessing *Est-2⁰* allele were more tolerant than those with *Est-2¹* and *Est-2²*. Taichung 65 is known to show cold tolerance at the vegetative phase, but susceptibility at the reproductive phase.

This raises the question whether the isozyme polymorphism for *Est-2* locus

Isozyme polymorphism for 3 isozyme loci -- *Amp-3*, *Est-2*, and *Pgi-2* -- at vegetative and reproductive phases.^a IRRI, 1988.

Cultivar	Isozyme pattern					
	<i>Amp-3</i>		<i>Est-2</i>		<i>Pgi-2</i>	
	V	R	V	R	V	R
IR36	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²
IR64	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²
Taichung 65	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ⁰	2 ²	2 ¹	2 ¹

^aV = at vegetative phase, R = at reproductive phase.

observed at vegetative and reproductive phases in Taichung 65 and other rice cultivars can be related to their cold tolerance at the two growth stages. □

Inheritance of high density grain in rice

S. Mallik, A. M. Aguilar, and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, IRRI

The parents, F₁, and F₂ of a cross of diverse parents IR30 and IR32385-37-3-3-3 (high density grain index [HDI] 56% and 29%, respectively) were grown in the greenhouse during 1987 wet season to study inheritance of this trait.

HDI was calculated by dividing the number of high density grains (specific gravity >1.20) by spikelets per panicle on primary (Pb) and secondary (Sb) branches (50 panicles of each parent and